

Title: The Party in Private Business: Institutionalizing Party Cells in Chinese Business

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ABSTRACT

In the early 2000s, the Chinese Communist Party (CCP) began reassessing its relationship with capitalism, notably with private entrepreneurs. During the following decade, the CCP embraced the private sector in a strategy of “co-optation” and private entrepreneurs joined the Party in increasing numbers. From 2012, the new Xi administration pushed for stronger political allegiance from all enterprises, resulting in a shift from “State Capitalism” to “Party-state Capitalism”. As a result, Party cells within enterprises of all ownership types have surged. The article investigates the intricate relationship between the Party and private businesses under Xi Jinping. The article employs a two-pronged approach. It examines policy documents and analyzes four recent case studies from Guangdong based on interviews and company documents. Our main finding is that while the push for Party integration has been significant, the role and influence of Party cells vary notably across private enterprises. Key words: Chinese Communist Party; party building; party-business relations; private sector economy; state capitalism.

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